

Physicochemical studies on uranium(VI) complexes of *N,N*-dialkylamides

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Uranyl dinitrato complexes $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ with two *N,N*-dialkylamides, viz. *N,N*-dihexyloctanamide (L^1) and *N,N*-dihexyldecanamide (L^2) have been synthesized. IR spectra reveal that the amide molecules are O-bonded to U and both the nitrate ions act as bidentate groups. Visible spectra indicate the formation of a monodentate inner-sphere metal-amide complex. PMR spectra of the complexes indicate the presence of restricted rotation around the C-N bond. The variable temperature PMR studies suggest a dynamic equilibrium between the coordinated and free amide molecules. Thermal investigations reveal that decomposition proceeds in three TG stages with four exothermic DTA steps corresponding to the release of two molecules of amides and two nitrate groups, finally leading to U_3O_8 .

Tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP) has been successfully used for nuclear fuel reprocessing in the PUREX process¹. However, the deleterious nature of its radiolytic/hydrolytic degradation products influence the decontamination factors (D.F.'s) of Pu and U with respect to fission products and increase the losses of Pu towards aqueous raffinate. Organophosphorous compounds in view of their lack of complete incinerability results in large secondary waste volumes. *N,N*-Dialkylamides (Fig. 1) have been proposed as alternative to TBP in view of their potential to overcome some of these problems associated with TBP²⁻⁴.

($\text{R}' = \text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}$; $\text{R} = \text{C}_7\text{H}_{15}$, C_9H_{19})

Fig. 1. Structure of *N,N*-dialkylamides.

In the present work, synthesis and characterization of uranyl complexes of dihexyl octanamide as well as dihexyl decanamide were carried out employing PMR, IR UV/visible and thermal studies. Particular attention has been paid to investigate the cause of disappearance of three triplets in the PMR spectra (observed for free dialkyl amides) on coordination to uranyl ion. In this context PMR studies were carried out in the temperature range 213 K to 333 K. An attempt has also been made to understand the mechanism of thermal decomposition of these complexes.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the yellow uranium complexes lead to their formulation as $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}^1$ and $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}^2$.

IR spectra : The absence of IR band at 3100–3500 cm^{-1} precludes the possibility of the presence of water either as associated impurity or as coordinated to the metal ion, thus confirming the anhydrous nature of the complexes. The reduction of the stretching frequency of the carbonyl group of the free amide from 1640 to 1570 cm^{-1} in the complex was observed because of the coordination through oxygen atom. A similar shift in the carbonyl stretching frequency has been reported for U^{VI} -dioctylbutyramide where the metal amide forms strong bond through oxygen of the carbonyl group⁵. The insensitivity of the C-N stretching vibration (1110 cm^{-1}) on complexation suggests that the nitrogen atom of the amide group does not coordinate to the U^{VI} ion. Present investigations show the absence of ionic nitrate band ($\sim 1360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which is split into ν_1 and ν_4 (symmetric and asymmetric stretching mode of the nitrate groups). All nitrate groups are covalently bound to uranium. Totally six nitrate vibrations ($\nu_1 = 1525$, $\nu_2 = 1030$, $\nu_3 = 750$, $\nu_4 = 1275$, $\nu_5 = 730$ and $\nu_6 = 815 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were identified. A wide variation ($\nu_1 - \nu_4$) of around 250 cm^{-1} indicates the bidentate nature of the nitrate group⁶. A strong band at around 935 cm^{-1} could be attributed to the O-U-O asymmetric stretch in the uranyl complexes⁷. Thus it is likely that the coordination number of U in uranyl nitrate - L^1/L^2 complexes is eight and the uranyl group is surrounded therein by four oxygen atoms from the bidentate nitrate group and two oxygen atoms from L^1/L^2 , lying in a plane perpendicular to the axial uranyl group.

Electronic spectra : The spectra of the uranyl nitrate-amide complexes were recorded after their dissolution in benzene. The peaks observed at 422, 434, 449 and 464 nm for U^{VI} in 3.0 M HNO_3 were shifted to 428, 441, 456 and 473 nm in the case of uranium - L^1/L^2 complex. In addi-

Table 1. Thermal decomposition data and kinetic parameters for the U complexes

Stage no.	DTA peak temp. °C (Exo)	TG temp. (°C)*			Wt. loss (%) : Expt.	Product (Theor.)	ΔE kJ mol ⁻¹
		T _i	T _s	T _f			
UO₂(NO₃)₂·2 L¹ :							
1	220 290	200	285	295	61.9 (61.2)	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	59.5
2	330	305	325	345	65.9 (66.5)	U ₂ O ₅ (NO ₃) ₂	35.5
3	470	355	470	500	73.1 (72.4)	U ₃ O ₈	30.0
UO₂(NO₃)₂·2 L² :							
1	290 320	220	310	325	63.8 (63.3)	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	112.8
2	400	335	420	450	71.0 (70.8)	U ₄ O ₁₁ (NO ₃) ₂	45.1
3	500	480	820	900	73.8 (73.9)	U ₃ O ₈	30.0

*T_i = Initial decomposition temperature, T_s = decomposition maxima temperature, T_f = final decomposition temperature.

tion, three new peaks were observed at 410, 421 and 490 nm. These bathochromic shifts and the emergence of new peaks in the complex indicate bonding through the oxygen of the amide. A similar spectrum obtained for the organic phase after U^{VI} extraction by L¹, suggests that uranyl ion was extracted with a similar structure even in solution phase.

PMR spectra : The PMR chemical shifts of various protons in L¹ and L² showed five sets of signals as follows : (1) L¹ = -N-CH₂- : 4 p, 3.20 (t) 3.11 (t); -CO-CH₂- : 2 p, 2.18 (t); -CH₂- : 6 p, 1.54 (t) and 1.42 (d); -(CH₂)_n-CH₃ : 20 p, 1.20 (d); -CH₃ : 9 p; 0.82-0.78 (m) and (2) L² = -N-CH₂- : 4 p, 3.11 (t) and 3.06 (t); -CO-CH₂- : 2 p, 2.13 (t); -CH₂- : 6 p, 1.51 (t) and 1.37 (s); -(CH₂)_n-CH₃ : 24 p, 1.15 (d); -CH₃ : 9 p, 0.77-0.70 (m) [p : protons, s : singlet, d : doublet, t : triplet, m : multiplet and numbers refer to chemical shift values in ppm]. As expected methylene protons adjacent to the N are deshielded maximum and those of terminal methyl group are deshielded minimum. As a consequence of the conjugation between the carbonyl and the nitrogen non-bonding electron pairs, the enhanced double bond character of the C-N bond restricted its rotation at room temperature. It results in the non-equivalence of the two methylene groups adjacent to N which are either *cis* or *trans* to the anisotropic carbonyl group and each of them appeared as a triplet due to the coupling of adjacent methylene protons.

The chemical shifts of various protons in the U^{VI} complexes of L¹ and L² show six sets of signals as follows : (1) UO₂(NO₃)₂·2L¹ = -N-CH₂- : 4 p, 3.61 (s) and 3.45 (s); -CO-CH₂- : 2 p, 2.68 (s); -CH₂- : 6 p, 1.71 (s); -(CH₂)₃-

CH₃ : 6 p, 1.32 (s); -(CH₂)_n-CH₃- : 14 p, 1.18-1.06 (m); -CH₃ : 9 p; 0.86 (t), 0.73-0.64 (m) and 0.71 (t) and (2) UO₂(NO₃)₂·2 L² = -N-CH₂- : 4 p, 3.62 (s) and 3.46 (s); -CO-CH₂- : 2 p, 2.69 (s); -CH₂- : 6 p, 1.71 (s); -(CH₂)₃-CH₃ : 6 p, 1.32 (s); -(CH₂)_n-CH₃ : 18 p; 1.16-1.07 (m); -CH₃ : 9 p; 0.87 (t), 0.76 (t), 0.66 (s). Additional set arises due to the distinct peak of (six) methylene protons which appeared originally in the uncomplexed amide as a part of methylene protons denoted as -(CH₂)_n-CH₃. Downfield shift (0.5 ppm) in methylene protons adjacent to C=O groups indicates bonding through carbonyl oxygen.

It was interesting to note (Fig. 2) that triplets observed for methylene protons adjacent to >N as well as >C=O groups (in ligands) are seen only as broad singlets on coordination to uranium. To understand this behavior PMR

Fig. 2. Variable temperature PMR spectra of UO₂(NO₃)₂·2 DHOA.

spectra of the $U^{VI}-L^1$ complex were recorded at variable temperatures in the range 213–333 K. Broad singlets in the complex observed at ≥ 298 K tend to reappear as triplets at 273 K. Very clear three triplets were observed at 233 K as well as 253 K corresponding to the three methylene groups. In addition, three triplets of significantly lower intensity were also observed which could be attributed to those of the uncomplexed ligands. It appears that the fast dynamic equilibrium between the free and complexed L^1 at room temperature (which is otherwise slow at lower temperature) is responsible for reducing the life-time (Δt) of the methylene protons in a particular chemical environment leading to the poor resolution and a broad singlet. On further decrease of temperature to 213 K, triplets again appear as broad singlet. This is explained as due to the increase in viscosity leading to decrease in T_1 (spin lattice relaxation time) as well as the decrease in the life-time of the excited methylene protons.

Thermal studies : The thermal decomposition studies of the U^{VI} complexes in air showed three main stages in its decomposition (Table 1) as follows : Step-1 corresponding to the release of two amide molecules, Step-2 corresponding to the formation of the polymeric species $U_2O_5(NO_3)_2$ in case L^1 and $U_4O_{11}(NO_3)_2$ in case of L^2 (Formation of these species has been reported previously by Addison *et al.*⁸) and Step-3 corresponding to the formation of U_3O_8 , thereby confirming the completely incinerable nature of the amides. The end-product formed was also identified in the case of L^2 complex by X-ray diffraction studies using $CuK\alpha$ radiation. The d -values (Å) with corresponding relative intensities calculated from X-ray diffraction pattern of end product were obtained as 7.83 (19), 4.16 (89), 3.41 (100), 2.63 (74), 2.07 (25), 1.95 (24), 1.77 (56) and 1.58 (15). These values agree with the literature values given for U_3O_8 ⁹. Whereas the first TG step corresponds to two DTA exothermic peaks, each of the second and third TG steps corresponds to single DTA exothermic peaks.

The higher initial decomposition temperature (T_i) for $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2L^2$ as compared to that of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2L^1$ indicates a greater thermal stability in case of the former complex. Occurrence of a DTA peak without any distinct step in TG for both the complexes suggests that the product formed is not stable under the experimental conditions. The kinetics of the different stages of decomposition as seen from the TG curve was also investigated following various approaches reported in the literature¹⁰. TG data for all three steps were found to fit well to Horwitz-Metzger's method for the kinetic analysis of non-isothermal data of a first order reaction. The activation energy (ΔE) values calcu-

lated from the TG curve by this method for the different stages of thermal decomposition of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2L^1/L^2$ are also summarized in Table 1.

Experimental

Uranium(VI) stock solution was prepared by dissolving nuclear grade U_3O_8 powder (Uranium Metal Plant, BARC) in nitric acid. Acyl chlorides and dialkylamine (Merck-Schuchardt) were used.

Synthesis of the amides : L^1 and L^2 were synthesized using the respective acyl chloride and dihexyl amine in the presence of triethylamine in ether at 0–5°. The reaction mixture was then washed with alkaline/acidic aqueous solution and distilled water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and purified by vacuum distillation (yields 80–90%) : L^1 , m.p. 183–185° (0.2 mm Hg); L^2 , 203–205° (0.2 mm Hg). Both gave satisfactory elemental analyses, and were characterized by IR and PMR spectra. Their purity was ascertained by the determination of amide contents using non-aqueous potentiometric titration¹¹. The results showed that the products were >99% pure.

$U^{VI}-L^1/L^2$ complexes : The complexes were prepared using solvent extraction method by saturating the 1 M extractant solution in benzene with uranyl nitrate by repeated contacts with ~60 mg/ml solution of U^{VI} in 3 M HNO_3 . The saturated organic phase was then separated, scrubbed with 3 M HNO_3 , dried with anhydrous sodium sulfate and evaporated to dryness. The yellow complexes thus obtained were crystallized from *n*-hexane : $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2L^1$, m.p. 34.5°; $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2L^2$, 57.5°. The compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

C, H, N were analysed on a Carlo-Erba EA 1110 analyzer. M.ps. were determined using a Mettler FP-61 apparatus. Uranium was estimated by reported method¹¹. Electronic spectra (benzene) were recorded on a Beckman DU-7 spectrophotometer, IR spectra (nujol/film) on a Pye-Unicam 9512 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Bruker 300 MHz instrument employing TMS as an internal standard. The thermal studies on the complexes were carried out in a flow of dry air employing DTA and TG. Thermograms were recorded at a heating rate of 5°/min upto 500° and at 10°/min at 500–850° in a ULVAC thermoanalyzer using sintered Al_2O_3 as the reference material for DTA.

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